

Role of E-Book in Enhancing Reading Skills at BS Level

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TABLE OF CONTENT

Chapter 1	819
Introduction.....	819
Research Question.....	819
Thesis Statement.....	819
Chapter 2	820
Literature Review.....	820
Chapter 3	821
Methodology.....	821
Sample.....	821
Method for Data Collection.....	821
Research Tools.....	821
Development of Questionnaire.....	821
Structure of Questionnaire.....	821
Implementation.....	821
Chapter 4	822
Data Analysis.....	822
Graphical Representation of Data.....	822
Chapter 5	829
Discussion.....	829
Chapter 6	830
Conclusion.....	830
Appendix	831
References	832

ABSTRACT

This study intends to uphold the role of e-book in enhancing reading skills. The role of e-book in present time is very much important to enhance the reading skills of students at university level which was negated so far by the earlier researchers. The present study conducted survey in order to collect data from students of BS. The data was collected from forty students at BS level selected from the University of Sargodha Mandi Bahauddin Campus in district Mandi Bahuddin. The findings of this research based on survey demonstrates that students are inclined toward using e-book for enhancing their reading skills which also meets the need of present time.

Keywords:- E-Book, Traditonal Book, Technology, Reading Skills

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

In the past few years, technology has really been pushed into educational classroom settings. Teachers are now able to use Smart Boards to do interactive read alouds with the class. Students are able to complete math and reading assessments through multiple effective computer programs, etc. Students also may have iPads, tablets, or computers at home that they are constantly drawn to for entertainment purposes. These technological tools are leading to gaining student interest. However, even though students are drawn to using a tablet for gaming purposes, using eBooks on tablets can be effective for literacy development. Using eBooks for student development in literacy is an important topic to research. An eBook can be an effective tool that can gain student interest and motivate them to complete the task at hand. According to Brown (2016), literacy involves understanding all forms of meaning that are represented within a set of social practices embedded in culture. In order to incorporate literacy into classrooms, teachers must come up with using different literacy practices within the classroom. A child should be able to “actively read, interpret, talk back to texts, as well as identify the many visible and invisible messages that comprise these texts” (Harste, 2010, p, 32). In the 21st century, a child must be able to use both a print and technology based text that connects in and out of school events.

Exploring the use of electronic books in the literacy classroom is significant because the students of today are growing up in an increasingly technological world. Most children are surrounded by electronics from birth, and have never known life without the Internet. Many students spend time at home engaged in technological activities such as watching television or DVDs, using Smart Phones, listening to CDs, and playing video games. Therefore, it is important for educators to keep up to date with the digital age to support them. Larson and Marsh (2005) state that it can help bridge the gap between home and school literacies when teachers integrate technology such as electronic books into the literacy classroom. Students who enjoy technology in their daily lives may be more likely to read and remain engaged in books that are presented in an interactive digital format. Introducing children to electronic books at a young age will also help them become familiar with technology and gain valuable twenty-first century skills that will help them throughout their lives.

In order to explore the role of electronic books on the reading experience of students, The researcher conducted survey on students of BS, a questionnaire was prepared on which student responded. The researcher have determined that electronic books effect and plays important role in enhancing reading skills increasing the motivation and engagement of Students at all levels, strengthening the reading comprehension of struggling readers, aiding their word reading abilities through supportive features.

➤ *Thesis Statement:*

Electronic book plays inevitable role in present time by enhancing reading skills by increasing motivation and engagement of students at all level.

➤ *Research Question:*

- *What is the Role of E-Book in Present Time?*
- *How E-Book helps in Enhancing Reading Skills?*
- *How E-Book is More Preferable than Traditional Book?*

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

The integration of technology in public schools has produced significant changes in educational settings: “The technologies of literacy are rapidly changing. Today, children need to be prepared for much more than book literacies” (Leu, 2000, p. 424). Researchers Colwill and Gallagher (2007) agree with Leu, and argue that what children need to learn and how they learn has notably changed with the integration of technology. Most public schools in the United States now provide students with opportunities.

Numerous studies have shown that students today are highly motivated by technology (Larson, 2010; Moody, 2010; Gainer & Lapp, 2010, Lankshear & Knobel, 2003). Reading electronic texts on digital tools such as an e-reader, CD-ROMs, or the internet is exciting to students who engage in the use of technology outside of school in their daily lives. Oakley (2008) explains that the dynamism inherent in video, animation, and sound seem to be appealing to today’s students, who are often used to the action and visuals inherent in TV and video games (p. 246). Students have a desire to read electronic books because they find them to be a new and unique medium that is multimodal, multisensory and interactive (Larson, 2010). Electronic books make sustained and repeated readings more attractive to students because they want to try out the number of digital options available, which helps them internalize the text and story content (de Jong & Bus, 2002). Prior to discussing how electronic books provide.

Parents can engage with children in multiple ways daily with language and reading. Agreeing with Han and Pritchett, Wilder (2014) states “the impact of parental involvement on student academic achievement has been recognized by teachers, administrators, and policy makers who consider parental involvement to be one of the integral parts of the new educational reforms and initiatives”. Parents should make sure they are devoting high levels of engagement when reading to or with their child due to the literacy achievement it can lead to in a child’s schooling. The advancement of literacy skills is directly determined by the regularity and condition of a child’s exposure to home literacy.

Jackson, O’Brien, Pisano, Rutkowski, & Smayda, (2014). Not only can high exposure to home literacies show a higher academic literacy achievement, it may also lead to a child’s interest in reading and writing. One reason that electronic books have been found to motivate children is that they are individual, private, yet supportive reading environments. Many students who lack motivation to read suffer from embarrassment because they struggle with literacy (Oakley & Jay, 2008). These children may experience social discomfort when working through a text at school or at home and come to the conclusion that they cannot read. Computers and handheld electronic reading devices offer a personal, safe reading context where embarrassment can be minimized (Oakley & Jay, 2008). Tools and features of electronic books scaffold literacy learning and can make difficult readings easier for struggling readers or English Language Learners so that they can independently read texts (Moody, 2010). If students do not know a word that they encounter, it can be pronounced and defined for them through narration and dictionaries, so they do not have to give up reading a text that is above their reading capabilities (Grimshaw, Dungworth, McKnight & Morris, 2007). Struggling readers or English language learners no longer have to go to an adult or peers for assistance, which allows them to save face when reading as well as time because they do not have to wait for their teacher and break their engagement with the text (Oakley & Jay, 2008; Grimshaw et al., 2007). The stress free environment that electronic texts provide makes students more likely to read and reread.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

➤ *Methodology*

So as to conduct present research, quantitative methods were given preference so the nature of the research is quantitative. Quantitative approach helped to collect data BS level. In order to collect data survey was conducted for the present study.

➤ *Sample:*

The participants of this case study were from Districts Mandi Bahauddin. The present investigation used sample of 40 participants. The data was collected from the students of BS English, University of Sargodha Mandi Bahauddin.

➤ *Methods for Data Collection:*

The researcher prepared close ended questions and acquired response through this survey from the students of BS English (University of Sargodha Mandi Bahauddin Campus).

➤ *Research Tools*

The present research was carefully managed questionnaire was taken as a tool to conduct this survey in district Mandi Bahauddin.

➤ *Development of Questionnaire:*

Present survey comprises of fifteen close ended questions and it covered each aspect to know about increasing reading skills through e-book. Questionnaire was formalised with the goal that respondent may give the exact information. It was attempted to utilize conceivable basic wording for survey, biased questions were avoided, all questions were about the topic.

➤ *Structure of Questionnaire*

The structure of the questionnaire is straightforward, simple and to the point that the respondents can comprehend and fill it without confronting any inconvenience. There were fifteen questions. The respondents were requested to tick one out of five choices these, choices were:

- *Agree*
- *Strongly Agree Neutral*
- *Neutral*
- *Disagree*
- *Strongly Disagree*

➤ *Implementation:*

After planning the survey and preparing the questionnaire Student of BS from university of Sargodha Mandi Bahauddin campus were selected to conduct this study. So, the questionnaire was handed over to participants in person. They filled in questionnaire and returned it to the researcher.

CHAPTER FOUR DATA ANALYSIS

➤ *Graphical Representation of Data*

Fig 1 I Like being Best at Reading

Question one was about being best at reading. 58% people agreed that they are best at reading. 26% students strongly agreed that they are best at reading. There was any response regarding being neutral but 11% student disagreed and did not show any interest on reading where as 5% people strongly disagreed when they were asked about being best at reading. The result of the first question showed that 58% percent students says that they are very much good at reading and there are less students who are not good at reading.

Fig 2 I am a Good Reader

The second question was about being a good reader. When students were asked to answer 33% students showed their interest in reading, 40% students strongly agreed that they are good reader. Only 1% students were neutral about being a good reader. 23% students disagreed and 3% students strongly disagreed that they are not good reader. The result of this question showed that majority of the students were inclined toward reading books and they were fond of reading all types of books.

Fig 3 E-Book helped me in Increasing My Reading Skills

Third question was e-book helps in increasing reading skills or not. 31% students agreed that e- book helps in increasing reading skills. 52% students strongly agreed that e-book actually helped students to increase their reading skills. Only 1% students remained neutral. 8% students disagreed that e-book did not helped them in increasing their reading skills and habit. 8% students strongly disagreed that e-book never helped them in enhancing reading skills. The result of this question show that majority of students who use technology said that e-book helped them in increasing their reading skills. Students who were not very much involved in technology saidit never helped them in increasing reading skills and they preferred traditional books for reading.

Fig 4 I Read E-Book to Learn New Information

Fourth question was related to learning new information via e-book. 50% students agree that they learn new things while reading e-book. 27% students strongly agreed that they get new information while reading on e-book.17% students disagreed on this question and said they never learn new things via e-book and 6% students strongly disagreed that they also never learnt any new things while using e-book. The result of this question shows that 50% of the students usually learn new information. As e-book is directly connected with technology when students face any difficulty they consult internet to overcome difficulty that arises during reading. E-book also contain hyperlinks which connect the reader with other information to make things more comprehensible. Another marked feature of e-book is that it always remain up to the date which helps student to be kept in touch with present things.

Fig 5 I Face Difficulty while Reading E-Book

Fifth question was about difficulties that arise while using e-book. 20% students agreed upon the difficulty that arises while using e-book. 10% students strongly agreed that they face difficulty while using e-book. Only 2% students were neutral about the difficulty that arises while using e- book. 38% students disagreed on this question. 30% students strongly disagreed that they do not face difficulty while using e-book. The result shows that majority of students disagreed that they do not face difficulty while using e-book.

Fig 6 E-Book Reading Improved my Vocabulary

Sixth question was regarding improving vocabulary by reading e-book. 45% students agreed that their vocabulary has been increased by using e-book. 18% students strongly agreed that their vocabulary is increased by using e-book. 4% students were neutral about the vocabulary where as 24% students disagreed and 9% students strongly disagreed on this question. The findings shows that while using e-book it is easy to see the meaning of difficult word which in result makes the word easy to memorize.

Fig 7 The use of E-Book has Increased the Amount of time I Spent Reading

Seven question was about the use of e-book and the time increased in reading. 32% students agreed that e-book has increased the amount of time they spent on reading. 23% students strongly agreed that using e-book had made them a goof reader.27% students disagreed that reading-book has no effect on them and 18% students strongly disagreed. The result shows that majority of the students said that using e-book has increased the time of reading as e-book is easily portable and accessible. There is not any difficulty while using e-book for students, even they prefer to use e-book than traditional book.

Fig 8 The use of E-Book has Increased the Variety of Books I Read

Eight question was about the use of e-book and the variety of books students read. 45% students agreed that the variety of e-book also increased while using e-book. 20% students strongly agreed. Only 2% students were neutral about the variety of books. 23% students disagreed and said that using e-book did not increased the variety of books students read. 10% students strongly disagreed on this question.

Fig 9 E-Book Reading has Made me to Develop Good Reading Habbit

Eight question was about reading e-book and developing good reading habit. 50% students agreed and said that e-book has made them to develop good reading habit.20% students strongly agreed where as20% students disagreed that students did not developed reading habit while using e-book.20% students strongly disagreed that e-book did not helped them in developing reading habit.

Fig 10 I can Geteasily the Desired Book in form of E-Book

Nine question was students can get easily their desired book in form of e-book. 39% students agreed that they can get easily desired book in form of e-book. 30% students strongly agreed thatthey can get the book they like. 3% students were neutral in their response. 18% students disagreed and 10% students strongly disagreed that they cannot get their favorite books in formof e-book. The result show that students are more prone to use e-book these days and they can get their desired book anywhere from internet with free of cost so, mostly students like to read one-book because it is free of cost.

Fig 11 Traditional Book Helped me in Increasing Reading Habit

Ten question was about traditional book and its effect on increasing reading habit. 20% students agreed on this question. 15% students strongly agreed on this question that traditional book helped them to increase reading habit. As students who are not interested in using technology or who do not have access to technology disagreed on this question. On the other hand 15% students were neutral for this question and 30% students disagreed that traditional book never helped them in increasing reading habit. 20% student again strongly disagreed that traditional book never helped them in increasing reading habit.

Fig 12 Traditional books help me more in developing reading skills

Eleven question was regarding developing reading skills by using e-book.18% students agreed and 14% students strongly agreed that traditional book helped them in increasing reading habit.9% students were neutral regarding this question. Whereas, 36% students disagreed and 23% students strongly disagreed on this question. The result shows that in present time students are more inclined toward using e-book rather than traditional book.

Fig 13 Traditional Book Helped me More in Developing Reading Skills

Twelve question was about developing reading skills by using traditional books.10% students agreed that traditional books helps in developing reading skills. 15% students strongly agreed that traditional book helps in developing reading skills. 10% students remained neutral for traditional book reading. 40% students disagreed on this question that it never helped in developing reading skills. 25% students strongly disagreed and preferred e-book reading. The result of this question show that traditional books are limited to provide skills to students on the other hand e-book has more to offer.

Fig 14 Traditional Books Helped me to Overcome Reading Difficulty

Thirteen question was regarding traditional books to help students in overcoming reading difficulty. Only 8% students agreed that traditional books help them in overcoming reading difficulty. 8% students strongly agreed where are 4% students were neutral about traditional book overcoming difficulty in reading. 46% students disagreed and said reading difficulty that traditional books never helped them in overcoming reading difficulty and 34% students strongly disagreed on this question that traditional book never helped in overcoming reading difficulty.

Fig 15 E-Book Helped me to Overcome Reading Difficulty

The fourteen question was, e-book helps to overcome reading difficulty. 48% students agreed that e-book helped in overcoming reading difficulties. 22% students strongly agreed that e-book helps in overcoming difficulties. 26% students disagreed on this question and only 4% students strongly disagreed. The result shows that students use e-book to overcome the difficulty that face during reading. While reading on e- book students are exposed to technology where they can check the pronunciation and difficult meanings of the word where as in traditional books it is far difficult for students to check for correct pronunciation and meanings of the words.

Fig 16 Reading on E-Book is More Enjoyable than Traditional Book

Last question was whether e-book is more enjoyable than traditional book, 20% students agreed that e- book is more enjoyable. 50% students strongly agreed on this question and they showed their preference on using e-book than traditional book. On the other hand no student gave response on neutrality. 5% students disagreed on enjoying e-book rather than traditional book.25% student strongly disagreed. The result of this question showed that students are more inclined toward using e-book than traditional books. There are many reasons for this, the basic one is e-book is easily accessible for students.

CHAPTER FIVE DISCUSSION

Findings of the present research with reference to role of e-book in enhancing reading skills demonstrates that technology has really been pushed into educational classroom settings. Teachers are now able to use Smart Boards to do interactive read alouds with the class. Students are able to complete math and reading assessments through multiple effective computer programs, etc. Students also may have iPads, tablets, or computers at home that they are constantly drawn to for entertainment purposes. These technological tools are leading to gaining student interest. However, even though students are drawn to using a tablet for gaming purposes, using eBooks on tablets can be effective for literacy development. An eBook can be an effective tool that can gain student interest and motivate them to complete the task at hand. According to Brown (2016), literacy involves understanding all forms of meaning that are represented within a set of social practices embedded in culture. A child should be able to “actively read, interpret, talk back to texts, as well as identify the many visible and invisible messages that comprise these texts” (Harste, 2010, p, 32). In the 21st century, a child must be able to use both a print and technology based text that connects in and out of school events.

As indicated by the present study, respondents have believed in the use of e-book for enhancing their reading skills. In this study, it was discovered that the students of BS level were more inclined toward using e-book for enhancing their reading skills. Respondents also presented their views about using traditional book, majority of the students were not satisfied with the use of traditional book as traditional books are difficult to manage and to carry along with. Traditional books are not easily accessible and informative. On the other hand e-book are more accessible and easily portable. If a student is reading on e-book is actually exposed to the world he can get any information via e-book.

The result shows that only small quantity of people from disagree on using e-book for enhancing reading skills. Greater amount of students agrees upon the statement that e-book helps in increasing and developing reading skills in comparison with traditional book. Most of the population strongly agreed that it is e-book through which students are learning new things. Findings also shows that the use of electronic books in the classroom is significant because the students of today are growing up in an increasingly technological world. Most students are surrounded by electronics from birth, and have never known life without the Internet. Many students spend time at home engaged in technological activities such as watching television or DVDs, using Smart Phones, listening to CDs, and playing video games. Therefore, it is important for educators to keep up to date with the digital age to support them. Larson and Marsh (2005) state that it can help bridge the gap between home and school literacies when teachers integrate technology such as electronic books into the literacy classroom. Students who enjoy technology in their daily lives may be more likely to read and remain engaged in books that are presented in an interactive digital format rather than using traditional books. Introducing children to electronic books at a young age will also help them become familiar with technology and gain valuable twenty-first century skills that will help them throughout their lives.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION

In a Nutshell, the aim of present study was to explore the role of e-book in enhancing reading skills. This study conducted survey by collecting data in form questionnaire from groups of students of BS English (University of Sargodha, Mandi Bahauddin Campus) in district Mandi Bahauddin. Drawing upon the result of respondents it was found that, students in present time are more inclined toward using technology and e-book reading is becoming more in day by day. Students are using e-book rather than traditional books and it is also helping them in increasing their reading skills.

APPENDIX

Name_____

➤ *Survey Research Questionnaire*

Department_____

• *Note:*

The researcher is an MPhil student who wants to explore the attitudes of students on multimedia learning versus traditional learning. This is purely an academic research. Your responses are voluntary and will remain confidential. I greatly appreciate your sincere responses.

Key SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, N=Neutral, DA= Disagree, SDA=Strongly Disagree Read the statements carefully and tick the most appropriate answer

Table 1 Survey Research Questionnaire

S. No	Statements	SA	A	N	DA	SDA
1.	I like being best at reading					
2.	I am a good reader					
3.	E-Book helped me in increasing my reading skills					
4.	I read e-book to learn new information					
5.	I face difficulty while reading e-book					
6.	E-book reading improved my vocabulary					
7.	The use of e-book has increased the amount of time I spent reading					
8.	The use of e-book has increased the variety of books I read					
9.	E-book reading has made me to develop good reading habit					
10.	I can get easily the desired book in form of e-book					
11.	Traditional book helped me in increasing reading skills					
12.	Traditional books help me more in developing reading skills					
13.	Traditional books helped me to overcome reading difficulty					
14.	E-book helped me to overcome reading difficulty					
15.	Reading on e-book is more enjoyable than traditional book					

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